

Effective Implementation of The Universal Basic Education Program in Secondary Schools: The Roles of Parents and Teachers in Kwara Central.

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Abstract:

This study investigated the roles of parents and teachers in the effective implementation of the Universal Basic Education (UBE) program in secondary schools within Kwara Central, Nigeria. Utilizing a descriptive research design, the study examined the level of involvement parents and teacher involvement in the UBE program in Kwara Central Senatorial District. The population comprised all parents and teachers of JSS 1 and JSS 2 students in public secondary schools across the four local government areas of Kwara Central: Ilorin West, Ilorin East, Asa, and Ilorin South. Simple random sampling technique was employed to select five schools from each of the local government areas, totaling twenty schools. Purposive sampling technique was used to select ten parents and ten teachers from each school, resulting in a total of 400 respondents. Data were collected using a self-designed questionnaire titled 'Parents Teachers Involvement on Modalities for the Implementation of UBE Questionnaire' (PTIMIUBEQ). The findings underscored the critical role of teachers, whose high level of involvement significantly enhances the program's implementation, contrasted with the average involvement of parents, which

suggests areas for potential improvement in parental engagement. The study recommended regular organization of workshops and community meetings to raise awareness among parents about the importance of their active involvement in the UBE program, creation of formal structures like Parent Teacher Associations (PTAs) where parents and teachers can meet regularly as well as the introduction incentive programs such as recognition awards, certificates, reduced school fees or subsidized school materials for parents who actively participate in their children's education.

Keywords: Parents, Teachers, Implementation, Universal Basic Education

Introduction

It is impossible to overstate the role that education plays in the growth of Nigeria, the global community, and governments everywhere. One of education's most crucial functions is to prepare students to adapt to the changing values of the world's quickly changing civilizations. According to Nwaka (2016), education serves as a means of imparting values to individuals, preparing them for acceptance into society and a fulfilling existence. In her various assessments of education policies, the

Nigerian federal government sought to solve the issues surrounding Education For All (EFA). For example, the 1976 introduction of the Universal Primary Education (UPE) program attempted to end illiteracy in the nation. Due to poor implementation brought on by insufficient finance, the UPE initiative was abandoned (FRN, 2013).

The current Universal Basic Education (UBE) introduced in 1999, in Nigeria is another giant move to eradicate illiteracy, ignorance and poverty. To effectively implement the goals of UBE, parents and teachers should be actively important stakeholders in the education of the child. In view of this point, Odekunle & Okuwa (2012) asserted that if there are pupils/students, infrastructure and other facilities but no teacher to give effect for them, education may not have taken place adequately. He further asserted that the teacher is a major force in determining the quality and even the quantity of education in the school therefore making the teachers the pivot on which all education system revolves.

Supporting the above statement, Gabriel (2013) highlighted that teachers' characteristics affect the quality of education in schools. Teachers remain the major source of students' learning of values, skills and knowledge making the teachers the main actors in educational scene. No educational reform can be effective without agreement, support and co-operation of teachers who are the chief executors and implementers. For this reason, teachers should always be given the opportunity to express their views in relevant educational issues.

Parents as well are important agent in the implementation of UBE programme. The UBE program aims to be free, mandatory, and universal. These words suggest that every Nigerian child of school age would have access to the right kinds of opportunities for their basic education. In light of this,

parents must make sure their children attend school in order to receive this free education; otherwise, the functions that instructors play are meaningless. Adebisi (2006) was of the view that, traditionally, parental involvement in education involved supporting their kids' school-based and home-based activities (e.g., helping with homework, encouraging reading, and attending school) as well as attending meetings of the Parents Teachers' Association, parent-teacher conferences, and fund-raising events. According to Famade (2012), parents' interest in school events and active participation in their kids' schoolwork are signs of parental involvement in their kids' education nowadays. Fund-raising, inter-house athletics, participation in school decision-making, information sharing, kid monitoring, and enforcing staff and student discipline are a few of these activities. According to Akinwunmi (2004), a key element in raising the efficacy of school children through higher-quality instruction is parental involvement in the classroom.

In this instance, parents visit their children's schools to meet with teachers and counselors, taking time off from their jobs to do so. In this way, they are informed about their children's abilities and are able to find ways to offer solutions, like getting tutors to assist with their children's extra tuition, giving them the learning resources they need, assisting their kids in sticking to their study schedules and studying appropriately, and so on. Parents are active in their children's education in a variety of ways. Parents can serve as classroom teachers at times and as active members of the Parents/Teachers Association, according to Todowedo (2006), parents can act as their child's classroom teacher, be active members of the Parents/Teachers Association, be a part of the school's program decision-making team, and help their child at home with homework assignments, projects, and other learning activities. A high level of parental

involvement will undoubtedly spur primary education to more effective and efficient performance. Gabriel (2013) added that parental involvement is not a friendly acquaintance with teachers but obligations from parents. This participation must be seen in the area of development of educational policies and curriculum issues that affect the destiny of children.

Therefore, when the Obasanjo administration implemented Universal Basic Education (UBE) in 1999, it did not make any mistakes. This UBE is designed for all persons who may have left school in any manner, not just those enrolled in primary and junior secondary education. Nwaka (2016) asserts that UBE offers a range of formal, informal, and non-formal education in addition to reading, writing, and numeracy abilities. Consequently, the Basic Education stresses nine (9) years in primary school, as opposed to the previous six (6) years. This implies that a child would spend three years in Lower Basic Education, three years in Middle Basic Education, and three years in Upper Basic Education.

In addition, all Nigerian children, including teenagers and adults, who are not enrolled in school, are entitled to the Universal Basic Education. In addition to moral, ethical, and civic principles, this will help students attain and acquire high-quality numeracy, reading, communication, and life skills. This initiative also addresses children attending daycare centers, kindergartens, and nurseries, as well as the children of pastoral nomads and migratory fishermen. The government has constructed schools for these individuals who travel from place to place. Its scope, structure, and nature are all broader than those of the former Universal Primary Education program (UPE). To ensure that everyone has access to free basic education, the Nigerian government launched the Universal Basic Education initiative in 1999.

In the past, attempts to improve education in the nation have failed, and this scheme has also been devised. Although there have been some recent improvements in Nigeria's school enrollment rate, the country's educational system continues to rank extremely poorly overall in international rankings.

Parents and Teachers as Stakeholders of UBE

Nigerians are eager to see the success of the Universal Basic Education programme, therefore all hands must be on deck to make it happen. For the programme to be effective, the government, parents, educators, and even the general public must cooperate, according to the stakeholders. Children should not be marginalized in any way that would prevent them from obtaining a well-rounded education that will promote their development in the fields of education, society, technology, economy, and morals as well as aid in the nation's growth, since children are the center of education.

This calls for parental involvement in education, or more specifically, for parents to contribute to their children's education, which would eventually lead to the much-desired consequence of stability and progress within the country. Akinrotimi & Olowo (2016) state that a child's performance in school has traditionally depended on the involvement of their family. In addition, parents can help their kids with school-related activities by volunteering for fund-raising events, attending parent-teacher conferences and seminars, and buying school supplies. Parents can help their kids with their homework, promote reading, and help with school attendance at home. Parents' enthusiasm in academic endeavors and active involvement in their children's schooling are now indicators of their involvement in their education, according to Adebisi (2016). Raising funds for school projects, playing interhouse sports, attending parent/teacher

association meetings to influence school policies, exchanging information, monitoring students' academic achievement, and enforcing staff and student discipline are a few of these.

According to Abu, Made, and Ajaero (2015), parental involvement in the educational process has a significant role in enabling schoolchildren to receive a high-quality education and become more effective learners. In this case, parents should visit their children's schools and schedule meetings with instructors and counselors while taking a break from work. This helps them come up with solutions and provides them with an update on their children's academic development. Getting tutors when necessary, offering extra aid, providing their children with the required learning resources, and motivating them to follow a study schedule are a few of these alternatives.

Parents are active in their children's education in a variety of ways. Jaiyeoba and Todowede (2012) state that parents occasionally take on two roles: they help their children with learning activities at home, such as writing assignments and projects, and they are active members of the Parents/Teachers Association. They also occasionally serve as members of the school's decision-making team regarding specific programs. Despite the various ways that parents can be involved in their children's education, numerous studies have demonstrated that many parents are unable to do so for various reasons, which makes them barriers to their children's academic success. Odekunle & Okuwa (2012) discovered that many parents have fallen into poverty as a result of difficulty and are unable to support their children in the ways that matter most, including buying textbooks, buying school supplies, getting them quality medical care, and much more. The majority of students have left school for these reasons.

Gabriel (2013) discovered that the lack of payment of school fees, books, other educational supplies, and uniforms can be attributed to parental dispossession resulting from death, divorce, or the disappearance of one of the parents. He went on, "Such a child may be a truant and as a result, adversely affecting his academics." He also underlines the fact that a large number of kids whose parents were not actively involved in putting UBE into practice did not follow school policies. They engage in a number of unethical behaviors at school, such as completing homework late, buying inappropriate textbooks, and cheating on tests. Other bad behaviors include not showing up for class on time or frequently, as well as displaying messy personal habits.

As it has been explained thus far, the Universal Basic Education (UBE) seeks to educate all of its residents from childhood through adulthood. For this program, which is both formal and non-formal, to be fully realized, parents' support is required for both individuals and groups. Parents are expected to participate in the Parents-Teachers Association (PTA) interactive process in order to stay informed about the school system, particularly with regard to the provision of text books and other learning aids for their children. This is because parents want to see their children occupy enviable positions in society (Iyanga, 2012). The data should illustrate both the advantages and disadvantages of providing or not providing textual materials for children's education. According to Nwaka (2016), parents bear the greatest responsibility for their children's upbringing because they have the most in-depth knowledge of them.

As a result, parents should set up their kids for success in life by giving them access to food and educational resources, as well as the proper emotional environment that will facilitate a seamless transition to school and

encourage curiosity and a positive attitude toward learning. She continued by saying that certain familial environments, such as physical deprivation, child abuse, arguing or rejection, and parental injustice, set the stage for early emotional stress. These circumstances frequently cause significant stress on a kid's emotional growth during their primary school years, which prevents the youngster from reaching the school's academic requirements.

The Parents-Teachers Association was established because of the beneficial effects it has had on children's welfare. This indicates that in order to effectively convey knowledge to the child, parents and instructors should collaborate. This is due to the fact that whatever a child learns at home is applied in the classroom and in other non-school settings. Therefore, parents keeping an eye on their child's actions will help reveal the abilities or shortcomings of the class teachers. Parents can use the PTA to voice their concerns if they feel that the teachers are not equipped to care for their children. In order to provide a remedy by obtaining qualified ones, parents would also let others know about this. When qualified teachers are not promptly assigned to the school, the PTA can help by hiring teachers, primarily on a part-time basis, to help until the Ministry of Education hires some instructors.

Additionally, by helping with classroom construction, parents can collaborate with the PTA to provide their children with a conducive learning environment, which will lessen the workload for the teachers. Parents will only be prepared to share a sense of purpose if they understand that teachers and parents are working together as a team to educate the children, according to Bruwer, Hartel, and Steyn (2014), mutual regard and openness to involvement. They clarified that parental

involvement entails parental obligations rather than just a cordial relationship with instructors. This involvement is clearly seen when it comes to curriculum development and policy formulation that impact children's futures. Without a doubt, a high level of parental participation will drive elementary education to function more effectively and efficiently. According to Nwaka (2016), mothers were more engaged in their kids' schooling than fathers were. Gabriel (2013) asserts that mothers should take an active role in their children's academic success because they typically celebrate it too much. He also suggests that parents frequently use their line of work as an excuse to avoid being involved, although even working-class moms make school visits for their kids.

On the other hand, teachers are also regarded as the main actor in schooling of the pupils. This means that without the teachers, there is no school. School cannot function without the teachers. The involvement of the teachers in the effective running of the UBE hereby becomes very vital. There are many ways through which a teacher can be effectively involved for the efficacy of the programme. Some of the suggested ways through which the teachers can be actively involved are by, having a regular in-service training. The in-service training is believed to equip them with Information Communication Technology (ICT). They should also carry out Continuous Assessment of their students for proper evaluation of their students; this would enable them to know if their students are diligently meeting up with the objectives of setting up UBE. Paying of regular salaries, provision of health facilities and promotion of the teachers as and when due is a motivational factor that can improve the efficacy of the UBE.

Conceptual Framework

This illustration shows that good involvement of parents and teachers as stakeholders of the UBE should either produce a positive or negative outcome. This is what this study is expected to discover. However, the researcher expects a positive outcome from the combination of both modalities.

In spite of all the effort made by the Nigerian governments on UBE programme aimed at providing free and compulsory basic education for every Nigerian child of school-going age, the implementation of the programme are still facing a lot of challenges ranging from lack of quality personnel, infrastructural facilities, and instructional materials to parental involvement. These factors have made the objective of the programme difficult to achieve, therefore this study tends to discover if the parents and the teachers can play some roles which can make the programme more effective. This research tries to fill the gap of study to find out ways in which parents and teachers could be

involved in effective implementation of UBE in Kwara Central.

Thus, the study's primary goal is to determine how parents and educators could contribute to the successful implementation of UBE. Thus the study investigated:

- i. the involvement of parents in the effective implementation of UBE in Kwara State.
- ii. the involvement of teachers in the effective implementation of UBE in Kwara State.

Methodology

This research adopted descriptive research design. The descriptive survey method enabled the researcher to get comprehensive information concerning the current status of the phenomena to explain the opinions, attitudes, feelings, beliefs and the behaviour of the study population in line with the study variables hence making it easier for the studied phenomena to be described exactly as they exist. The population for this study consisted of all parents and teachers of JSS I and II students in public secondary schools in

Kwara Central. There are four local governments in Kwara Central. Simple random sampling technique was used to select five schools from each of the four local government areas making twenty schools. The local government areas in Kwara Central are Ilorin West, Ilorin East, Asa and Ilorin South Local Government Areas. Purposive sampling techniques was used to select 10 parents and teachers from each of the five selected schools giving 200 parents and teachers with the total sum of 400 respondents. A self-designed questionnaire titled 'Parents Teachers Involvement on Modalities for the Implementation of UBE Questionnaire' (PTIMIUBEQ) was developed for the study. Each item had Likert type scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and

Strongly Disagree (SD) at the end of the statement. Both face and content validity of the instrument were ascertained by experts from the relevant fields. The test-retest reliability method was used to ascertain the reliability of the instrument while the two scores were correlated using Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation producing a reliability index of 0.72.

Results (Expected outputs/Results):

Research Question 1: What is the level of involvement of parents in the effective implementation of UBE in Kwara State?

Table 1: Level of involvement of parents in the effective implementation of UBE in Kwara State

	Parents involvement	Mean	SD
1	Feel well-informed about the goals and objectives of the Universal Basic Education (UBE) program through school communications.	3.50	.87
2	I am regularly updated about my child's progress and the implementation of UBE through newsletters or other school communication channels.	2.95	.67
3	The school provides adequate opportunities for me to participate in Parent-Teacher Association (PTA) meetings.	2.75	.77
4	I have access to training and workshops that help me support my child's education effectively.	2.90	1.05
5	I feel that my input and feedback on school policies related to UBE are valued and considered by the school administration.	3.00	.55
6	The school provides me with resources and materials to support my child's learning at home.	3.05	1.12
7	I am encouraged to volunteer in school activities and contribute to the implementation of UBE.	2.75	.89
8	Community meetings held by the school are effective in addressing concerns related to UBE and in involving parents	2.85	.91
	Weighted mean	2.97	

Key : 1 – 1.59 - Low; 2.00 -2.59 – Average; 3.00 – 4.00 - High

Table 1 shows the level of parental involvement in the effective implementation of UBE in Kwara State. It shows that all the presented items were agreed upon by the

respondents. Items 1, 6, 5 were the 1st, 2nd and 3rd respectively in terms of parental involvement. The weighted of 2.97 is an indication that the parents were moderately involved. Therefore, the level of parental

involvement in the effective implementation of UBE in Kwara State was average.

Research Question 2: What is the level of involvement of parents in the effective implementation of UBE in Kwara State

Table 2: Level of involvement of teacher in the effective implementation of UBE in Kwara State

	Teachers involvement	Mean	SD
1	I receive adequate training and professional development to effectively implement the Universal Basic Education (UBE) program.	3.45	.810
2	The school administration provides sufficient resources and materials to support the UBE curriculum in my classroom.	2.90	.439
3	I am regularly involved in discussions about the development and refinement of UBE-related policies and strategies.	3.10	.894
4	I have opportunities to collaborate with colleagues on UBE-related initiatives and share best practices.	3.15	.915
5	I am encouraged to engage with parents to support the effective implementation of UBE in my classroom.	2.95	.870
6	The school actively seeks my feedback on the implementation of the UBE program and considers my suggestions for improvement.	2.95	.926
7	I have access to and utilize student performance data to adjust my teaching strategies in alignment with UBE goals.	3.10	.773
8	There are clear guidelines and support systems in place to help me understand and apply the UBE curriculum effectively.	2.80	1.130
	Weighted mean	3.05	

Key : 1 – 1.59 - Low; 2.00 -2.59 – Average; 3.00 – 4.00 - High

Table 2 shows the level of involvement of teachers in the effective implementation of UBE in Kwara State. It shows that all the presented items were agreed upon by the respondents. Items 1, 4, 3 and 7 were the 1st, 2nd and 3rd respectively in terms of teachers' involvement. The weighted of 3.05 is an indication that the teachers were more involved. Therefore, the level of involvement of teachers in the effective implementation of UBE in Kwara State was high.

The level of parental involvement in the effective implementation of the Universal Basic Education (UBE) program in Kwara State has been assessed as average. This assessment is based on various studies that highlight both the strengths and weaknesses

of parental engagement. While some parents actively participate in school activities and support their children's education at home, a significant number of parents remain disengaged due to factors such as lack of awareness, socio-economic challenges, and limited educational background. This has implications for the overall effectiveness of the UBE program, as parental support is crucial for reinforcing the educational efforts made by schools and teachers. Apebende, Akpo, Idak and Ife (2010) found that parental involvement was significantly lower than expected, with female parents being more involved than their male counterparts. This trend suggests that targeted interventions are needed to enhance parental engagement, such as community awareness programs and support systems for parents. By addressing these gaps, the UBE program can

achieve better outcomes in terms of student performance and overall educational quality.

The level of involvement of teachers in the effective implementation of the Universal Basic Education (UBE) program in Kwara State has been notably high. This high level of teacher involvement ensures that educational policies and curricula are effectively delivered, thereby enhancing student learning outcomes and overall program success. The commitment of teachers in Kwara State is further evidenced by their active participation in continuous professional development programs and their engagement in school development planning. This is supported by the finding of Omosidi, Saheed & Abdulyaqin (2017) which found that teachers in Kwara State frequently attend workshops and training sessions designed to improve their teaching skills and adapt to new educational methodologies. This proactive approach not only boosts their teaching efficacy but also aligns with the goals of the UBE program to provide quality basic education to all children. The high level of teacher involvement, therefore, plays a crucial role in the effective implementation of the UBE program, ensuring that educational standards are maintained and improved over time.

As a result, the study recommends regular organization of workshops and community meetings to raise awareness among parents about the importance of their active involvement in the UBE program highlighting the critical role that parents play in supporting their children's education, providing guidance on how they can effectively participate in school activities, monitor academic progress, and collaborate with teachers; creation of formal structures like Parent Teacher Associations (PTAs) by schools, where parents and teachers can meet on regular basis to discuss the progress of the UBE implementation as well as the

introduction incentive programs such as recognition awards, certificates, reduced school fees or subsidized school materials for parents who actively participate in their children's education.

Data Availability Statement

The primary data used to support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author/s upon request.

Contribution/ Originality: The management of Universal Basic Education, the government, policy makers, Parents, Teachers, the general public and future academics are all expected to greatly benefit from the study's findings, which indicates that there would be more effectiveness in the implementation of the UBE if the parents and teachers work hand in hand in progress of it.

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